

Airline Captain's Case Study of Jet-Engine Oil Based Contaminated Cabin Air

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ABSTRACT

This presentation shows a case study based personal experience of the author as an airline pilot. It is an overview of the cause and effect of contaminated bleed air on pilots and their acute symptoms on their cognitive capacity commandeering an aircraft after inhalation of toxic fumes and the dangers of such concerning their responsibility for the safety of passengers and crew. The materials presented causing this effect are pyrolyzed oil fumes from jet-engine oil and their ability of long-term injuries of the nervous system and a very certain but common diagnosed lung diffusion impairment after experienced fume events.

INTRODUCTION

It is shown that the inhalation of these fumes can lead to various acute, uncontrollable disorders and can also result in excessive damage due to oxidative stress to the central nervous system. This review gives details about some acute toxicity mechanisms, along with their long-term health effects.

Michael Kramer (MK) started his career as a military aircraft mechanic and later received his A/P from the Lufthansa Technical Training school. After leaving the military he worked as an aircraft mechanic and then as an engineer on executive aircraft (and engines).

He started flying as a pilot on Turboprops like Metroliner and Jetstream 31 for three years, following BAe146 for two years, then Bombardier CRJ-100 to -900 series aircraft for ten years and Airbus A300 for almost four years. In total almost 19 years of commercial aviation.

While flying the BAe146 he smelled and subsequently inhaled a lot of engine oil fumes on a regular basis, especially in the mornings after auxiliary power unit (APU) start. He never experienced a fume event with visible smoke or haze. There were some incidents when crew became incapacitated at which time he already flew the brand new Bombardier CRJ's. But by the time he left the BAe146 for the new fleet, he realized that his immune system was very low while experiencing many more sinus colds than would be the norm. In the ten years of flying CRJ's he never experienced a fume event and his health recovered. Even the lung performance reached almost 100% again. Then he changed the company and started to fly the A300-600.

After having experienced several (well documented) smell and fume events, his last flight ever took place on September 3rd 2015 with yet another fume event. He encountered several fumes or 'smell events' with engine oil or minor exposures to jet fuels, either at engine start up or shut down but he did not notice his health degrade significantly. He also gained weight with new digestion problems and developed food allergies; initially he put it down to age, the kind of job, but never toxic cabin air.

Convinced that the authorities would take proper action if there were any danger for crew and passengers he continued trusting the system. His attitude changed after his experience on his last flight with the massive exposure to pyrolyzed engine oil fumes due to broken seals, after which he developed long lasting health symptoms.

The event

They had oil smell right after take-off. As pilot in command (PIC) MK gave it a try and switched pack no. 1 'off' with the result that the smell disappeared. Upon arrival the engineer transferred it to the 'Hold Item' list

and labelled pack no. 1 'INOP'.

The second leg was a short low-level positioning flight into Heathrow and there was no oil smell. The next leg from Heathrow to Leipzig and once again oil smell appeared right after take-off. When the smell increased MK switched the remaining pack no. 2 'off' and the 'INOP' labelled pack no. 1 'on' and the smell disappeared. As they were reaching cruise level with thrust reduction the smell reappeared again and got worse. He changed pack no. 2 to 'on' and no. 1 'off' and the smell disappeared. The next 45 minutes in cruise flight were uneventful and the pilots thought all was OK.

When they started descent procedures both pilots began to feel dizzy, nauseated and strangely fatigued. The oil smell started intensifying quickly and got worse again. Passing flight level 230, MK started the APU to get a third air source, but there was no improvement of air quality, so he switched 'off' all packs and bleeds and both pilots used their oxygen masks. Although they used the oxygen masks, they did not recover sufficiently to confidently land the aircraft manually. After landing in 'auto land' MK 'forgot' to disconnect the autopilot to vacate the runway.^{1,2} During 'shut down' the First Officer mentioned that all switches were covered with a fine layer of engine oil. The arriving maintenance crew confirmed the still present smell and told the pilots that this aircraft was known to have the problem.

The technical findings aftermath brought a leakage of bearing #2 back plate carbon seal on both engines to light, due to which the environmental control system (ECS) became severely contaminated with engine oil.³⁻⁵

After arrival at the local hospital the pilots received a medical examination according to a guideline of the employers' liability insurer 'Berufsgenossenschaft Verkehr' (BG).

After being checked at this hospital where the medical staff did not exactly know what they were looking for, the First Officer recovered fully after a few days; it had been his first fume event at the age of 26.

The Captain's (MK) overall symptoms in the first week were:

- 'high' feeling for 5 days
- extreme fatigue
- extreme headaches
- sleep disorders
- metallic taste

followed by:

- lasting cognitive and neurological impairment
- lasting respiration problems with the DLCO at only 66%
- pulmonary issues with some calcified nodules in his lungs⁶
- fibrosis
- small fibre neuropathy

At the time of this presentation, almost two years later, the airline's insurer had sent a report denying that contaminated cabin air was the reason for his long-term health problems and stopped monthly compensation.

The BFU (accident investigation agency) has not released their report yet.

CONCLUSIONS

Following his experiences with the authorities and medical establishment MK has founded the organisation 'P-COC' (Patient Initiative Contaminated Cabin Air e.V.) to:

- build a network to connect everybody that is involved e.g. crewmembers, passengers, physicians, scientist, attorneys, politicians etc.

to demand:

- that all aircraft are immediately equipped with sufficient protection for crew and passengers i.e.: masks, filters etc.
- immediate information of the public about the problem of contaminated cabin air by the responsible

representatives of industry and politics, as well as a general information requirement for passengers by the airline in the case of an incident with contaminated cabin air

- the immediate implementation of all prevention measures, e.g. crew training on proper reporting, health checks etc.⁷
- the proper investigation of fume events by the Bundesstelle für Flugunfalluntersuchung (BFU) according to EU-Regulation 996/2010
- the proper handling of occupational accidents with contaminated cabin air by the BG Verkehr according to prevailing law
- the complete scientific research of all circumstances causing incidents with contaminated cabin air by using all available resources and creating additional, independent institutions to support the process.
- the continuous monitoring of the cabin air on commercial aircrafts on toxic components by using the latest technology available

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